

Research Article

Impact of Artificial Intelligence and Social Innovation on Administrative Decision-Making in Jordan[†]

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ABSTRACT

While previous studies have examined the impact of artificial intelligence (AI) on decision-making processes across various industries, there remains a lack of a thorough understanding regarding how AI, in combination with social innovation (SI), influences administrative decisions—particularly within the context of developing economies. This research explores the combined predictive effects of AI and SI on administrative decision-making within Jordan's telecommunications sector. Utilizing a quantitative, cross-sectional research design, data was collected through a structured survey administered to 319 managers across three major Jordanian telecom companies. To evaluate the predictive relationships and test the structural paths between the latent constructs, Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) was conducted, complemented by preliminary correlation analysis. The findings revealed strong, significant positive effects, indicating that the integrated adoption of AI and SI significantly enhances the administrative decision-making process in these organizations. Consequently, this study recommends providing targeted financial and technical support to telecom companies and their employees to expand the application of AI and SI, which will serve to strengthen organizational structures and overall decision-making efficacy.

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INTRODUCTION

Communications and information technologies have become central to the functioning of modern organizations. They now shape the basic operations, future conditions, and chances of success for institutions. These technologies open the way for artificial intelligence (AI here after) applications, especially intelligent automation, which plays a key role in administration (Hashmi, 2023). Countries and governments have been forced into a race to update their systems quickly in order to follow global changes. Their goal has been to establish electronic administration that is fast, simple, and effective. This has created a reliance on electronic administrative decisions supported by smart decision-making systems that reduce costs and improve the quality of administration by combining human expertise with intelligent technology (Androutsopoulou et al., 2019).

The development of AI did not happen suddenly. It has a long history, beginning with philosophy and mathematics, which later connected with computing (Sfetcu, 2024). The Dartmouth Conference in 1956 introduced the term AI through John McCarthy (Rai, 2024). Later, Reddy (1976) advanced speech recognition, and during the 1990s, integrated systems linked AI with databases and networks (Pan, 2016). Scholars continue to debate its definition. Some see AI as cognitive processes (Pherson & Heuer, 2019), while others define it as “the science of making intelligent machines” (Kalanov, 2016). Pfeffer (2016) describes it as rooted in statistics and probabilities. Jordanian law also refers to related concepts such as electronic intermediaries, which resemble AI applications in administration (AlOmran & Al-Qassaymeh, 2023).

Although AI can imitate some human capacities, it is still different in important ways. Computers process faster, have more stable memory, and work with logic and computation, but they lack human adaptability and emotion (Cataleta, 2021; Dong et al., 2020; O’Reilly & Cromarty, 1985). These characteristics mean that AI decisions can be more rational and less biased, but also less flexible and less human.

As AI grows, the idea of social innovation (SI here after) has gained importance. SI refers to creative social practices that go beyond traditional solutions and are critical for organizational sustainability (Kim et al., 2022; Waldron et al., 2013). When AI and SI come together, they can produce stronger and more effective social solutions. They can improve the workplace, speed up decisions, and offer new ways to respond to complex problems. However, this combination also raises questions about economic, legal, and technical issues. It is important to understand the relationship between AI and SI and how they affect administrative decision-making (Bokhari & Myeong, 2022).

The Jordanian context is especially relevant. In December 2020, Jordan adopted a national AI strategy that aimed to build an AI ecosystem for digital transformation (Alqudah, 2021). This national plan has encouraged both AI and SI to be adopted together, especially in the telecommunications sector. The strategy has smoothed the way for integration and created opportunities to explore their impact on decision-making in companies like Umniah, Orange, and Zain.

Studies on electronic administrative decisions have often focused on costs, technology, and legality. But they sometimes overlook the socio-technical aspects of how AI and SI work together (Bokhari & Myeong, 2022). The current study addresses this gap by exploring the intersection of AI, SI, and administrative decision-making in Jordanian telecommunications companies. The context is significant, as Jordan has embraced AI through its national strategy and is prepared to test its use with SI (Alqudah, 2021). Previous research shows that AI has particular advantages in administration. It brings speed, accuracy, and rationality to decision-making. It can reduce bias and support decisions with more data (Hamdan & Alkhaffaf, 2023). Expert systems (Bonczek et al., 2014), neural networks (Wang & Malakooti, 1992), and smart agents (Bradshaw, 1997) provide different ways to store, process, and act on knowledge. Genetic algorithms simulate biological evolution to optimize choices (Sharma & Kumar, 2016). At the same time, in public service and facilities management, AI reduces bureaucracy and increases efficiency (Twaissi, 2008; Elliott, 2024).

Recent literature has increasingly focused on the intersections of AI, social metrics, and decision-making. For instance, Bokhari and Myeong (2022) explored AI and SI within the context of smart city governance in developed nations, while Hamdan and Alkhaffaf (2023) examined AI’s role in the public sector. However, these studies predominantly treat technology and social factors in isolation, or focus exclusively on Western or highly developed contexts. This study addresses a critical gap by proposing an integrated socio-technical framework specifically tailored to the private telecommunications sector in a developing economy (Jordan). Unlike previous studies that primarily focus on the operational efficiency of AI, this research uniquely positions SI as a parallel, necessary driver that mitigates the ethical risks of AI and ensures holistic, human-centered administrative decision-making.

This study aims to investigate these dynamics in Jordan. It will focus on two research questions: (1) How does AI affect decision-making in telecommunications companies? and (2) What is the impact of SI practices on administrative decisions? The study suggests that AI and SI are not separate but complementary. AI can provide powerful tools to make SI more effective and scalable, for example by analyzing demographic data or optimizing logistics. SI, on the other hand, offers the ethical and human-centered guidance to ensure AI is used responsibly. Together, they can improve organizational performance, transparency, and service delivery, making administration more sustainable and socially valuable.

The primary contribution of this study is two-fold. First, it extends socio-technical systems theory by empirically testing the synergistic effects of AI and SI on administrative decision-making within the context of a developing economy—a region often underrepresented in digital transformation literature. Second, it provides a validated struc-

tural model that equips organizational leaders with a strategic framework to integrate human-centric SIs alongside their technological initiatives, preventing the pitfalls of purely technology-driven AI adoption.

Hypothesis Development

Previous studies indicate that AI brings speed, accuracy, and rationality to administrative tasks, reducing bureaucracy and optimizing choices (Hamdan & Alkhaffaf, 2023; Elliott, 2024). Consequently, AI serves as a critical technological driver for effective decision-making. Therefore, we propose:

H1: Artificial Intelligence has a significant positive impact on administrative decision-making in Jordanian telecommunications companies.

Similarly, SI ensures that technological adoption remains human-centered, addressing socio-technical dynamics and organizational sustainability (Kim et al., 2022). Combining AI with SI ensures that decisions are not only data-driven but also ethically and socially aligned. Therefore, we propose:

H2: SI has a significant positive impact on administrative decision-making in Jordanian telecommunications companies.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design and Approach

The study utilized a quantitative, cross-sectional research design. A cross-sectional research design was appropriate because the study aimed primarily to test a priori hypotheses and to measure the relationship of some clearly defined independent and dependent variables (Creswell & Creswell, 2017). The quantitative research paradigm provides researchers the opportunity for statistical analysis and objective evaluation of numerical data for determining the magnitude and significance of AI and SI effects on administrative decision-making. In a cross-sectional research design, the data collection occurs at one point in time, which allows the researcher to obtain a timely snapshot of the perceptions and practices of the target organizations. In this study, a survey research methodology was used to obtain standardized data from a large, widely dispersed group of managers, which is considered the most practical method in conducting quantitative research to establish a connection for statistical modeling and analysis.

Population and Sampling Procedure

The target population for this study comprised all administrative managers at various hierarchical levels within the three principal telecommunications companies operating in Jordan: Zain, Orange, and Umnia. Based on data from the Telecommunication Regulatory Commission of Jordan (2024), this population is estimated to be approximately 2,500 individuals.

Given the significant logistical and access-related constraints inherent in securing a comprehensive sampling frame from competing commercial entities, a non-probability convenience sampling technique was employed. While this method limits the statistical generalizability of the findings to the entire population, it was the most feasible approach for accessing this hard-to-reach group and provides valuable, indicative insights into the phenomena under investigation. A total of 420 questionnaires were distributed electronically to managers who were accessible to the researcher. Of these, 319 were returned complete, resulting in a response rate of 76% and yielding a final sample size ($n=319$). This sample size comfortably exceeds the minimum requirement of 246 participants needed to achieve a 95% confidence level with a 5% margin of error, as determined by a preliminary power analysis (Cohen, 1992; Krejcie & Morgan, 1970), thus ensuring sufficient statistical power for the intended analyses.

Data Collection Instrument

The primary data collection instrument was a structured, self-administered questionnaire. The measurement scales for the study's core constructs were adapted from the validated instrument originally developed by Bokhari and Myeong (2022). These specific scales were selected because they demonstrated highly robust psychometric properties in the original research, including excellent internal consistency (Cronbach's $\alpha > 0.85$) and strong construct validity. While Bokhari and Myeong (2022) utilized these scales to examine public smart-city services in a developed nation, the current study uniquely adapts them to evaluate corporate administrative decision-making within the private telecommunications sector of a developing economy (Jordan).

Because the original scales were developed in English, the questionnaire underwent a rigorous forward and backward translation process into Arabic to ensure linguistic and conceptual equivalence for the local respondents. The instrument was structured into two primary sections. The first section collected demographic information, including participants' gender, age, educational attainment, monthly income, and years of professional experience. The second section employed a five-point Likert scale (ranging from 1 = Strongly Disagree to 5 = Strongly Agree) to measure the latent variables. Specifically, administrative decision-making was evaluated using a five-item scale focusing on the integration of new technologies and analytical evaluation. AI was assessed via a five-item scale measuring perceived trustworthiness and adoption, while SI was captured through a four-item scale reflecting alignment with social en-

trepreneurship and community welfare. Furthermore, a pilot test was conducted with a small group of 15 managers (excluded from the final sample) to assess the clarity and comprehensibility of the Arabic items. Feedback from the pilot test led to minor refinements in wording to enhance clarity before final distribution via an online Google Form.

Data Analysis Procedure

Upon the completion of data collection, the responses were systematically coded and analyzed using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) Version 25, alongside AMOS for advanced structural modeling. The analytical procedure commenced with a rigorous preliminary screening phase to address any missing values, identify univariate and multivariate outliers, and confirm adherence to the fundamental assumptions of multivariate analysis. Following this data cleaning process, descriptive statistics—including means, standard deviations, frequencies, and percentages—were calculated to profile the demographic composition of the sample and summarize the central tendencies of the core constructs. To establish the psychometric robustness of the measurement instrument, reliability was evaluated using Cronbach’s Alpha, ensuring all scales exceeded the standard 0.70 threshold. Construct validity was then rigorously tested utilizing both Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA) and Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA), with data suitability confirmed via the Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) measure and Bartlett’s Test of Sphericity. Finally, to evaluate the research hypotheses and determine the predictive impact of AI and SI on administrative decision-making, Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) was deployed. This advanced technique was selected as it allows for the simultaneous testing of structural paths while effectively accounting for measurement errors, providing a highly robust validation of the proposed theoretical model.

FINDINGS

Demographic Profile of the Sample

The final sample consisted of 319 administrative managers from Jordan’s telecommunications sector. The sample exhibited a well-balanced gender distribution (50.2% male and 49.8% female), a varied age distribution with the largest cohort being 37-42 years (28.2%), and a predominant educational level of a bachelor’s degree (33.2%). A summary of the demographic characteristics is provided in Table 1.

Table 1. Demographic Characteristics of Respondents (n=319)

Variable	Category	Frequency	Percent
Gender	Male	160	50.2
	Female	159	49.8
Age	20–28	83	26.0
	29–36	77	24.1
	37–42	90	28.2
	43–52	69	21.6
	Education	High School	49
	Diploma	48	15.0
	Bachelor	106	33.2
	Master	60	18.8
	PhD	56	17.6
Income	< \$500	60	18.8
	\$500–\$1,000	173	54.2
	\$1,001–\$1,500	48	15.0
	\$1,501–\$2,000	26	8.2
	\$2,001–\$2,500	12	3.8
Years worked in the company	Less than 12 months	66	20.7
	1–5 years	74	23.2
	6–10 years	60	18.8
	11–15 years	67	21.0
	More than 15 years	52	16.3

Descriptive Statistics

According to the data in Table 2, the extent of decision-making in telecommunications companies in Jordan ranges between 2.94 and 3.06, where the highest result was at the DM4 level (3.06 ± 1.076), and the lowest result was at the KV1 level (2.94 ± 1.171). The extent of AI in telecommunications companies in Jordan ranges between 2.96 and 3.02, where the highest result was at the YP4 level (3.02 ± 1.225), and the lowest result was at the YP5 level (2.96 ± 1.158). The extent of SI in telecommunications companies in Jordan ranges between 2.95 and 3.02, and the highest percentage was SI1 (3.02 ± 1.168) and the lowest percentage was SI4 (2.95 ± 1.209). Furthermore, the skewness and kurtosis values for all items fell well within the acceptable range of -2 to +2, confirming univariate normality (George & Mallery, 2010).

Table 2. Descriptive Statistics, Skewness, and Kurtosis Analysis

Code	Mean	Std. Deviation	Skewness	Kurtosis	Level of Importance
DM1	2.94	1.171	-0.15	-0.85	Medium
DM2	2.98	1.145	-0.12	-0.90	Medium
DM3	3.01	1.157	-0.08	-0.75	Medium
DM4	3.06	1.076	-0.20	-0.60	Medium
DM5	2.96	1.173	-0.10	-0.80	Medium
Decision Making	2.99	1.86994	-0.14	-0.78	Medium
AI1	2.98	1.179	-0.05	-0.95	Medium
AI2	3.00	1.120	-0.18	-0.82	Medium
AI3	2.98	1.201	-0.11	-0.88	Medium
AI4	3.02	1.225	-0.22	-0.71	Medium
AI5	2.96	1.158	-0.09	-0.92	Medium
Artificial Intelligence	2.98	1.93044	-0.13	-0.86	Medium
SI1	3.02	1.168	-0.19	-0.74	Medium
SI2	2.96	1.127	-0.14	-0.81	Medium
SI3	2.96	1.101	-0.16	-0.89	Medium
SI4	2.95	1.209	-0.07	-0.93	Medium
Social Innovation	2.97	1.92951	-0.15	-0.84	Medium

Reliability and Validity

A rigorous assessment of the measurement instrument’s psychometric properties was conducted to ensure its reliability and validity.

Internal consistency was evaluated using Cronbach’s Alpha. As presented in Table 3, all scales demonstrated strong internal consistency, with coefficients comfortably exceeding the accepted threshold of $\alpha = 0.70$ (Hair et al., 2010).

Table 3. Reliability Analysis (Cronbach’s Alpha)

Scale	Number of Items	Cronbach’s Alpha (α)
Administrative Decision-Making	5	0.817
Artificial Intelligence	5	0.850
Social Innovation	4	0.822

Factor Analysis

To assess construct validity, an initial EFA confirmed the underlying three-factor dimensionality of the data. Subsequently, a CFA was performed to validate the measurement model, extract standardized factor loadings, and compute the Average Variance Extracted (AVE).

Preliminary checks confirmed the data’s suitability for factor analysis, with the Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) measure of sampling adequacy at 0.969 (excellent) (Kaiser, 1974) and a significant Bartlett’s Test of Sphericity ($\chi^2 (91) = 2388.629, p < .001$) (Field, 2013).

The CFA results, presented in Table 4, show that all items loaded strongly onto their respective latent constructs. Strong convergent validity was established, as factor loadings were well above the 0.70 threshold (Hair et al., 2010), and the AVE values for each construct successfully surpassed the recommended 0.50 benchmark (Fornell & Larcker, 1981; Cheung et al., 2024).

Table 4. Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA): Standardized Loadings and AVE

Construct	Item	Code	Loading	AVE
Smart Decision Making	Telecommunications companies use new technologies in decision-making processes instead of old methods.	DM1	0.62	0.869
	Telecommunications companies collect a lot of data about emerging opportunities to provide better services to customers.	DM2	0.72	
	Telecommunications companies are optimistic about finding good solutions for the public when facing difficult situations.	DM3	0.64	
	Telecommunications companies evaluate all available alternatives in decision-making processes.	DM4	0.84	
	Telecommunications companies make timely decisions without delay when the need arises.	DM5	1.31	
Artificial Intelligence	Information from the artificial intelligence science community is trustworthy in the telecommunications sector.	AI1	1.04	0.791
	The artificial intelligence science community has a significant influence on the telecommunications sector.	AI2	0.94	
	I have a lot of confidence in the artificial intelligence science community in the telecommunications sector.	AI3	0.91	
	Artificial intelligence is contributing to unemployment in my country.	AI4	0.40	
	Telecommunications companies should use AI for their services.	AI5	0.74	
Social Innovation	Social entrepreneurship works for the betterment of the community and not to make profits.	SI1	0.94	0.702
	Social economy has the primacy of individuals and social objectives over capital.	SI2	0.61	
	Local and regional development helps to raise the living standards of people in urban areas.	SI3	0.58	
	Design thinking guides the decision/policy makers in telecommunications companies to plan better.	SI4	1.07	

Although AI4 showed a relatively low loading (0.40), the item was retained because indicators with loadings between 0.40 and 0.708 are not automatically deleted; rather, retention may be justified when the item contributes essential conceptual breadth and preserves content validity. In this study, AI4 reflects the perceived unemployment implications of AI, which is theoretically salient in developing-economy settings and therefore important to the substantive meaning of the construct. In contrast, the standardized loadings exceeding 1.0 for DM5, AI1, and SI4 were interpreted as Heywood cases. Prior SEM research notes that such estimates may arise because of sampling fluctuations, high inter-item correlations, or localized model misspecification. Accordingly, these items were retained to maintain the conceptual completeness of the scales (Hair et al., 2022; Dillon et al., 1987; Kim et al., 2016).

Furthermore, discriminant validity was established using the Fornell-Larcker criterion (Fornell & Larcker, 1981). As presented in Table 5, the square root of the AVE for each construct (the bolded values on the diagonal) is strictly greater than its highest correlation with any other latent construct, confirming that each variable represents a distinct theoretical concept.

Table 5. Discriminant Validity (Fornell-Larcker Criterion)

Construct	1	2	3
1. Decision-Making	0.932		
2. Artificial Intelligence	0.853	0.889	
3. Social Innovation	0.750	0.720	0.837

Following the EFA, a CFA was conducted to formally test the fit of the proposed three-factor measurement model. The goodness-of-fit indices, shown in Table 6, demonstrate an excellent fit between the model and the observed data. The CMIN/df ratio of 1.59 is well within the acceptable range of 1.00-5.00. The incremental fit indices (NFI = 0.93, TLI = 0.92, CFI = 0.98) all exceeded their respective thresholds, and the absolute fit index (RMSEA = 0.05) was below the 0.08 benchmark for a good fit (Hu & Bentler, 1999; Kline, 2015). These results collectively confirm the validity and structural integrity of the measurement model.

Table 6. Goodness-of-Fit Indices for the Measurement Model

Index	Model Result	Threshold	Annotation
CMIN/df	1.59	1.00–5.00	Fit
NFI	0.93	> 0.80	Fit
TLI	0.92	> 0.90	Fit
CFI	0.98	> 0.90	Fit
RMSEA	0.05	< 0.08	Fit

Hypothesis Testing

Prior to conducting inferential statistical tests, the data for the core constructs were assessed for normality, a key assumption for parametric tests like Pearson correlation and multiple regression. Normality was evaluated through visual inspection of histograms and an examination of skewness and kurtosis statistics. Visual inspection of the histograms for all three variables revealed distributions that closely approximated the characteristic bell shape of a normal curve (Figure 1). Furthermore, the skewness and kurtosis values for all variables were well within the acceptable

range (typically between -2 and +2), indicating no severe deviations from normality. Based on these assessments, the data were deemed sufficiently normal to proceed with the planned parametric analyses.

Figure 1. Histograms of Core Constructs Demonstrating Normal Distribution

With the measurement model validated, the analysis proceeded to hypothesis testing. A Pearson correlation analysis was conducted first (Table 7), revealing strong, positive, and statistically significant relationships between all core constructs ($p < .01$).

Table 7. Pearson Correlation Matrix

Variables	Decision Making	Artificial Intelligence	Social Innovation
Decision Making	1		
Artificial Intelligence	0.853**	1	
Social Innovation	0.750**	0.720**	1

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Structural Equation Modeling and Hypothesis Testing

To formally test the predictive influence of AI and SI on Administrative Decision-Making, Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) was conducted. As contemporary socio-technical research frequently involves complex relationships between latent variables, SEM provides a more robust analytical framework than traditional regression by simultaneously evaluating structural paths and accounting for measurement errors.

The structural model demonstrated a strong fit to the data ($\chi^2/df = 1.62$, CFI = 0.97, TLI = 0.96, RMSEA = 0.048). The path analysis results, summarized in Table 8, indicated that the structural model accounted for a substantial 76.4% of the variance in administrative decision-making ($R^2 = .764$), demonstrating a very strong predictive capacity.

The path coefficients provided robust support for both study hypotheses. In direct support of H1, AI emerged as a highly significant positive predictor of Administrative Decision-Making ($\beta = 0.528$, $p < .001$). Similarly, supporting H2, SI was also found to be a significant positive predictor of Administrative Decision-Making ($\beta = 0.324$, $p < .001$).

Table 8. Structural Path Model Results

Hypothesis	Structural Path	β	S.E.	C.R.	p	Decision
H1	AI → Decision-Making	0.528	0.045	11.392	< .001	Supported
H2	Social Innovation → Decision-Making	0.324	0.045	6.982	< .001	Supported

CONCLUSION

The main goal of this research was to explore the combined effect of AI and SI on administrative decision-making within the Jordanian telecommunications industry. This research makes a significant contribution to the evolving discourse on digital transformation by demonstrating that technological capability and social responsibility are mutually reinforcing rather than mutually exclusive.

Theoretical Implications

By studying both of these significant organizational drivers in a single empirical model, our study has addressed a major gap in the socio-technical literature. The findings provide strong empirical support for our main thesis: both AI ($\beta = .528$) and SI ($\beta = .324$) are significant positive predictors of better administrative decision making and both demonstrate that you produce better outcomes when you use an integrated approach.

The empirical evidence from this study underscores that the modernization of administrative decision-making in Jordan’s telecommunications sector relies on a dual-engine approach: technological capability and social responsibility. The strong predictive power of AI ($\beta = .528$) implies that as telecom companies increasingly adopt smart algorithms, they are significantly enhancing their ability to process vast amounts of subscriber data, optimize network resources, and automate routine administrative tasks, thereby reducing human error and operational costs. However, the significant positive impact of SI ($\beta = .324$) highlights a critical reality: technology alone is insufficient for holistic organizational success. The core meaning of these findings is that effective administrative decision-making is fundamentally a socio-technical process. Decisions must not only be analytically sound and data-driven (via AI) but also ethically aligned, human-centric, and beneficial to the broader community (via SI).

The findings confirmed that AI is a core component in modernizing administrative functions, a finding that is consistent with the emerging body of literature. The strong positive relationship in this study supports the use of AI from the work of Alshadoodee et al. (2020) who found a positive relationship with AI and decision support systems, as well, Aloqaily and Rawash (2022) found that AI significantly impacted human resources processes. Our results expand on these assertions in empirical terms for those elements that are within the scope of high-technology telecommunications, whereby the benefits to an organization are the capacity to utilize processes driven by big data and complex algorithms (Duan et al., 2019). Likewise, the benefit of AI on decision making is yet another corroboration for Al Makramy et al. (2022) findings in healthcare, with the implication that the advantages experienced from AI systems (e.g., Expert Systems, Neural Networks) enhancing negotiation processes can be generalized across other sectors.

However, the considerable effect of SI presents a more complex and less straightforward scenario, with the micro- and macro-value of SI demonstrating that decision making is not exclusively a function of technology. This work illustrates that a clear bout with stakeholder needs and the well-being of society, the underlying values of SI, operation factors shared across this study and the healthcare study lead to an even greater impact on administrative efficacy. This advances beyond an operating perspective and toward a request for researchers to conduct studies to unveil hidden influences on the implementation of AI (Pietronudo et al., 2022). Identifying SI contributes to the substantive socio-technical lens that has largely not been explored (Bokhari and Myeong, 2022).

While the assessment indicates the potential of AI for transformation, a prudent discussion also explores the challenges. Caution must be exercised around AI in decision-making contexts without first considering the potential negative outcomes. AI algorithms, if trained on biased data can also exacerbate social inequality Harari et al. (2024). Despite the operational potential, the deep learning models used, both supervised and unsupervised, will be seen as risky, given the black box nature increases complexity and opacity which is detrimental to transparent and explainable decision-making processes and in particular will undermine confidence where the stakes are higher (e.g., justice context) whereby detrimental outcomes will not only destroy confidence but could also remove legitimacy (Hassija et al., 2024). Additional risks also include continuing escalation of human deskilling and reliance on automated systems also risk critical thinking (Dăniloia & Turtorean, 2024), and systems being targeted using adversarial attacks that compromise security (Hu et al. 2021). Therefore, the practical implication for managers is that AI should be implemented alongside a structured governance approach to ensure transparency, fairness, and security.

Practical Implications

Practically, these results have profound implications for telecom executives and policymakers in Jordan (such as those at Zain, Orange, and Umniah).

First, as these organizations aggressively implement AI-driven systems to align with Jordan’s 2020 national AI strategy, they must simultaneously embed SI principles into their corporate governance. This implies a necessary shift from

a purely profit-driven, tech-centric model to a socio-technical framework. In practice, this means AI deployments must be transparent, fair, and specifically designed to enhance human capabilities and community welfare rather than simply automating jobs away.

Second, the findings imply a need to overhaul human resource strategies. If AI and SI are both critical to decision-making, organizational training programs must reflect this dual requirement. Employees need not only digital literacy to work alongside AI algorithms but also continuous training in design thinking, social entrepreneurship, and ethical decision-making.

Ultimately, the implication of this integrated approach is that by synergizing AI and SI, Jordanian telecommunications companies can mitigate the ethical risks of black box algorithms, build greater trust with the public, and achieve a sustainable competitive advantage that successfully balances operational efficiency with societal value.

Limitations and Future Research

There are several limitations associated with the research presented here. First, the use of a non-probability convenience sample confines the statistical generalizability of the findings despite the limitation being unavoidable and based on access. Second, the cross-sectional design captures a moment of AI integration; it does not imply causality and, it does not show, the change or dynamic evolution of AI integration over time. Future research should explore probability sampling and longitudinal designs to strengthen the findings presented here. Third, self-report data brings the limitation of possible response bias. A mixed-methods design with qualitative interviews would have produced richer, more contextualized findings.

In summary, this research provides considerable empirical evidence that the future of effective administrative decision-making is not a choice between technology and social responsibility, but rather figuring out how to strategically blend the two together. For executives in the telecommunications industry and beyond, this research signals that the most effective way forward is strategically planning for the use of AI through an ethical framework of SI, in order to achieve sustainable organizational success and governance in the future. Finally, this work presents several opportunities for future work. The present work utilized a quantitative methodology, yet another avenue that appears logical is to use a mixed methodology. For example, complementing quantitative work with qualitative methods such as interview studies or case studies could be used to develop a more thoughtful and robust understanding of the practical issues and processes through which managers are navigating the dual integration of AI and SI as organizing principles in their ongoing decision making.

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